

The Indian National Pension Scheme (NPS): A Retirement System that got even better

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ABSTRACT

In the age of Governments no longer providing formal social security post-retirement, individuals now have an increased need to build their retirement corpus. The Pension Fund Regulatory Development Authority (PFRDA) regulates India's National Pension Scheme (NPS) – a formal contributory pension system introduced in early 2000. The NPS is well designed and has a robust framework. Over the years, active regulation made the product more robust. NPS now allows individual Indian citizens (and not just Government or private sector employees) to subscribe and build their retirement corpus. Several regulatory developments and changes occurred during 2020-2021, making the product much better and more valuable to its subscribers. The recent steps taken by the pension fund regulations are positive, and foster increased penetration, development, and better services to pension funds subscribers. This article gives an overview of the recent reforms and explains the implications for various stakeholders, including pension fund subscribers who benefit from the reforms.

Keywords: *retirement planning, pension funds, market regulations, social security*

1. INTRODUCTION

Despite being the second-most populous country globally, India took a while to formally provide a framework for pension funds to all its citizens. Pension and retirement plans were earlier confined to Government employees only before India underwent pension reforms. Many developed and developing countries underwent pension reforms during the 1990s (Oladeinde, 2021). India stands at 19th position globally in terms of Retirement Sub-Index rankings.

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The rankings have improved from 36 (in 2018) to 27 (in 2019) to 19 (in 2020). Indian life expectancy is at 69 years. A large population in India is young. The ratio of 65+ years aged population against the population between 15 and 64 is a mere 6.2%. These numbers are the lowest amongst BRIC countries. Overall, India maintained its 44th rank (in 2018, 2019, and 2020) regarding the Global Retirement Index Ranking (Natixis, 2020). These factors highlight the need for a robust retirement planning fund for the Indian population.

Figure 1: Old-age dependency ratio and population aged 65 and above

Source: WDI/World Bank

Source: United Nations Population Division

The National Pension Scheme (NPS) became the pension fund of choice after the Government of India decided to stop its defined pension benefits to its employees who joined after April 1, 2004. The NPS is designed to be a voluntary defined contribution pension system. The NPS was made open and available for all citizens of India effective October 1, 2019. Any subscriber between the ages of 18 and 65 (recently changed to 70 years), including NRIs, Overseas Citizen of India (OCI) cardholders, and PIOs, can apply and contribute to their NPS account. The Indian NPS is akin to the 401(k) plans of the US.

The job of controlling the pension funds was entrusted to a regulator - the Pension Fund Regulatory Development Authority (PFRDA). The PFRDA established the NPS Trust on February 27, 2008. The NPS Trust is responsible for monitoring the operational and service level functions under the NPS (NPS Trust, 2015).

Over the years, the subscriber base has grown to 30 lakh voluntary non-government subscribers by 2021. Accelerated growth was witnessed in the recent five years. Back in 2018, the subscriber base was a mere 13.5 lakhs (Busi-

ness Line, 2021). As of June 30, 2021, the total subscribers under NPS and Atul Pension Yojna (APY) together are 435.36 lakhs. While the COVID-19 does impact the contributions by the subscribers, PFRDA feels the AUM growth would be above 30 percent for 2021-22.

Table 1: NPS & APY Subscriber base

Sector	June 2020 (in lakhs)	June 2021 (in lakhs)	YOY Growth (in %)	Share (in %)
Central Government	21.1	21.85	3.55	5
State Government	47.99	52.74	9.90	12
Corporate	10.13	11.74	15.89	3
All Citizen	13.06	17.46	33.69	4
NPS Lite	43.25	42.97	-	10
APY	215.46	288.60	33.95	66

Data Source: Pension Bulletin (PFRDA, 2021)

Pension fund assets under management (AUM) are growing at over 30% CAGR and recently have surpassed the Rs. 6 lakh crore mark. PFRDA expects that the total AUM would touch Rs. 7.5 lakh crore by the end of March 2022.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The key objective of this study is to examine the recent developments regarding the development of the National Pension Scheme (NPS).

3. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study is significant for individual NPS subscribers because it influences how they plan and make subscriptions to their retirement corpus. The study will also be useful for other stakeholders in the pension fund ecosystem, including the regulator, the pension fund houses, and other intermediaries.

4. LITERATURE SURVEY

A preliminary literature survey is undertaken to understand the previous research studies conducted on this topic. Our first understanding is that there is little research on this topic, and very few publications are found in leading research index portals. Surely, there is much scope for research on the subject.

India is a country with about 6.5 percent population considered elderly. As many as 80 million Indians are above the age of 65. Only a fraction of them is covered under social protection. Lack of awareness and poor income levels are reasons for the inability of many to join in contributory social insurance pension plans. Even those who joined had low retirement savings (Priyadarshee & Bhatnagar, 2021). NPS is found to be a simple retirement tool and a tax-saving

investment option. Removal of Goods and Services Tax (GST) on annuity has made it more attractive (Seethal & Menaka, 2018). An empirical assessment of various NPS schemes for the period 2015-2020 was done by (Kurmi et al., 2020). The study finds NPS to be performing well and that Tier II schemes had the edge over Tier I schemes. The NPS is a unique pension system because of its minimum processing charges, being market-linked, and providing tax-saving benefits – all in a single financial package (Kamath & Patil, 2017). (Murari, 2020) applied risk-adjusted evaluation measures such as Sharpe, Treynor, and Jensen's alpha on various NPS schemes. Following a case study approach of implementing Corporate NPS at an automobile manufacturing company, (Mohapatra & Veenu, 2019) found that the young workforce's lack of awareness and inclination towards savings are deterrents to NPS.

A. Research Gap

Having understood that the quantum of research done on Indian pension funds is significantly less than what the topic deserves, our next immediate focus is on the various areas within the concept of pension funds that have been unaddressed. This research article hence attempts to discuss recent regulatory updates related to the NPS.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Content analysis is applied in this research to systematically analyze content, make inferences, generate themes, and categorize the data to get credible and context-bound interpretations in the area of study. Secondary data is collected from the official websites of PFRDA, NPS Trust, and individual Pension Fund houses. Data is also collected from various newspapers, magazines, and research journals. Regulatory developments and events that happened during the period from 2020-2021 are studied and discussed in this research.

6. DISCUSSION

This study is of significance for individual NPS subscribers because it can potentially help them take key retirement decisions going forward.

A. Intermediaries

The robustness of NPS lies in its well-designed structural framework. PFRDA has specified the functions, selection/registration process, regulations, circulars, charges, and guidelines for each of them. Table 1 lists the intermediaries and a brief description of them.

Table 2: Intermediaries in National Pension Scheme Framework

Intermediary	Description
NPS Trust	Managed by a Board of Trustees, NPS Trust takes care of assets and funds of NPS in the interest of subscribers.
Central Recordkeeping Agency (CRA)	CRA provides the operational interface between the PFRDA and other NPS intermediaries. Currently, there are three CRAs: NSDL e-Governance Infrastructure Limited, KFin Technologies Pvt. Ltd., and Computer Age Management Services (effective March 30, 2021)
Pension Funds	Manages the pension fund corpus through various schemes and communicates
Trustee Bank	Provided day-to-day fund flow and banking facilities and transfers funds to intermediaries as per operational guidelines. Axis Bank is appointed Trustee Bank effective July 1, 2013
Custodian	Provides custodial and depository participant services for the pension schemes
Government Nodal Offices	Offices which act as an interface between the subscribers and the CRA and shall include the Directorate of Treasuries and Accounts (DTA), District Treasury Offices (DTO), and Drawing & Disbursing Office (DDO) under the State Government
Point of Presence (POP)	Interaction points for the registration of (first time) subscribers, undertaking and verification of Know Your Customer (KYC) details, receiving contributions and instructions from subscribers, and transmission of the same in the NPS architecture.
Retirement Advisers	Intermediaries who provide advice related to retirement planning and NPS
Aggregators	Intermediaries who perform subscriber service functions under NPS-Swavalamban in respect of their constituent groups.

Table 3: List of Pension Funds in India

Government Sector Pension Funds	Private Sector Pension Funds
1. LIC Pension Fund Ltd 2. SBI Pension Funds Pvt. Ltd 3. UTI Retirement Solutions Ltd	1. HDFC Pension Management Co. Ltd. 2. ICICI Prudential Pension Funds Management Company Limited 3. Kotak Mahindra Pension Fund Ltd. 4. LIC Pension Fund Ltd. 5. SBI Pension Funds Pvt. Ltd 6. UTI Retirement Solutions Ltd 7. Aditya Birla Sun Life Pension Management Ltd

In order to increase the penetration of the product further in Tier-I and Tier-II cities, the PFRDA has allowed individuals (including subscribers of NPS) to distribute pension products. Surely, this multiplies the marketing stream for the product and helps create awareness about the product in public.

B. Penny drop for subscriber validation

C. PFRDA took a new initiative to resolve problems faced in making payments when subscribers requested an exit or a partial withdrawal from NPS. It initiated an instant bank account verification system called “penny drop.” Through the penny drop process, CRA will be able to validate the bank account by transferring Rs. 1, which will validate all the required details as per the documents submitted by the subscriber (N. Saikat, 2021).

D. If the “penny drop” fails at the time of processing, the subscriber should inform to correct bank account no and resubmit the application so that payment will be made within the time limit. Moreover, CRA’s will inform not to modify existing bank account once the exit or partial withdrawal request is given till the amount is credited. If the details are not correct, alternate account details or supporting documents should be submitted and get the records updated.

E. The initiative can help timely credit of money and performing due diligence to identify the rightful beneficiary. This resolves typical subscriber problems such as the withdrawal amount that could not be credited, invalid bank account number or account type, invalid or wrong IFSC code, and name mismatch.

F. Change in age for NPS entry and exit

The PFRDA has increased the maximum entry age from the current 65 years to 70 years. Similarly, the NPS exit age limit has been upward revised from 70 years to 75 years.

G. Full withdrawal for smaller NPS corpus

An NPS subscriber, upon retirement, can withdraw 60 percent of the accumulated corpus as a lump sum and must buy an annuity plan for the remaining 40 percent. Buying an annuity from an ASP (Annuity Service Provided) is mandatory. As per the new norms, if the corpus is less than Rs. 5 lakhs, the entire corpus can now be withdrawn without the need to purchase an annuity.

H. Changes in Premature withdrawal norms

NPS provides a premature exit option in some cases. Any exit before three years is considered a premature exit. In this case, 20 percent of the accumulated corpus can be withdrawn as a lump sum, and the rest (80 percent) is

invested in life insurance. However, as per the changed norms, the entire corpus (if it is below Rs. 2.5 lakhs) can be withdrawn even before the retirement age.

Apart from premature withdrawal, partial withdrawal is also allowed. The partial withdrawal situation might arise for the subscriber at key money needs - health, marriage, education, or buying a house. The subscriber should have invested for at least three years, and the amount withdrawn should not exceed 25 percent of contributions. Partial withdrawal can be made a maximum of three times during the entire tenure of subscription.

I. Hike in NPS fee

NPS is an attractive long-term investment option because of its ultra-low-cost fund management fee structure. Pension funds are allowed to charge 0.01 percent, which is perhaps the lowest one can seek. No wonder many of the fund houses are running in losses because doing a low-margin business requires volumes. Though the NPS AUM base has witnessed an enormous increase, pension fund houses are barely at break-even levels in profits.

A new slab-wise fee structure was introduced effective April 1, 2021, which has allowed a better fee structure for the pension fund houses. According to this, pension fund houses can now charge an investment management fee from 0.03 percent to 0.09 percent per annum. Even the new fee structure is low, making NPS still an attractive low-cost, long-term investment option. Asset management companies have the dual job of generating good returns for their investors and yet bringing in profits to the fund management company. The closest alternatives to pension funds are mutual funds (whose expense ratio ranges from 0.05% to 2.5%)(SEBI, 2019). There are only a few debt ETFs that charge 0.05 percent or less.

Table 4: AUM Slab-based fee structure

AUM Slab	Investment Management Fee (% per annum)
Up to Rs. 10,000 crores	0.09
Rs. 10,001 crores to Rs. 50,000 crores	0.06
Rs. 50,001 crores to Rs. 1,50,000 crores	0.05
Above Rs. 1,50,001 crores	0.03

Table 5: AUM of various Indian Pension fund houses

Pension Fund House	June 2020 (in Rs. lakhs)	June 2021 (in Rs. lakhs)	YOY Growth (in %)	Share (in %)
SBI	178621	237567	33.00	38.53
LIC	134129	173547	29.39	28.15

UTI	135590	176338	30.05	28.60
Kotak	1143	1711	49.69	0.28
ICICI	5071	8369	65.04	1.36
HDFC	9972	18667	87.19	3.03
Birla	180	318	76.67	0.05

Data Source: NPS Trust; Reliance Pension Fund has surrendered their registration and ceased their operations

Table 6: Tier I Plan-wise AUM of various fund houses

Pension Fund House	TIER I			
	Equity Plans	Government Bond Plans	Corporate Debt Plans	Alternative Investments
Birla Sun Life Pension Scheme	136	95	63	1
HDFC Pension Fund	8,494	6,173	3,832	47
ICICI Prudential Pension Fund	3,482	2,961	1,827	11
Kotak Pension Fund	667	531	330	4
LIC Pension Fund	1,714	1,656	960	5
SBI Pension Fund	6,312	6,958	3,561	20
UTI Retirement Solutions	991	885	498	4

Data Source: ValueResearchOnline.com

Table 7: Tier II Plan-wise AUM of various fund houses

Pension Fund House	TIER II			
	Equity Plans	Government Bond Plans	Corporate Debt Plans	Tax Saver Plan
Birla Sun Life Pension Scheme	14	12	8	0.1
HDFC Pension Fund	409	318	206	1
ICICI Prudential Pension Fund	180	156	110	0
Kotak Pension Fund	49	37	24	0.1
LIC Pension Fund	70	123	47	0
SBI Pension Fund	262	276	157	1
UTI Retirement Solutions	52	41	24	0.19

Data Source: ValueResearchOnline.com

J. Better annuity options for subscribers

The mandatory annuity norm at the time of vesting the NPS corpus gives in a safety net for the subscribers because they can get pension monies for the rest of their life. Insurance companies offer annuity products in India, and unfortunately, they are not beating inflation. The real returns from the annuity (post taxation and inflation) are negative.

PFRDA requested IRDAI to bring in inflation-beating annuity products, such as variable annuities, for example, but the process is taking time (Srivats, 2021a). The delay is making PFRDA consider taking statutory backing and working out on products with different payout options and market-linked rates. One proposal is to allow fund managers to bring in a product that gives regular payouts to beat inflation but not necessarily on the same annuities lines. Also, proposals are considered to allow a structured process of systematic withdrawal or a payout within the funds.

Since the law mandates that NPS exit should only be through annuities, there is an immediate need to amend the same. PFRDA has sent a proposal to the Union Cabinet, and once the Cabinet approves it, a bill will be put before the Parliament to get approval and then enact the PFRDA Amendment Bill into law (Srivats, 2021d).

K. Investing in IPOs

The year 2021 is a milestone in Indian capital markets. Perhaps 2021 can be considered as the Indian Year of IPOs. With 38 IPOs entering the capital markets with a combined issue size of Rs. 71,833 crores till August 21, 2021 (Chit-torgarh, 2021) and more in the pipeline; 2021 is reporting the highest capital raising from the primary market in recent times. No wonder the RBI was seeing this as the beginning of a new era and has attributed to the trend as a “growth impulse igniting markets” (PTI, 2021).

PFRDA advised pension funds to formulate a detailed policy investment in IPO and get it approved by their boards. The investment team can decide on a day-to-day basis subject to compliance with the investment policy. The PFRDA has stipulated some conditions for such investments. Pension funds can invest only in equity shares of such IPO-bound companies where the full-float market capitalization per the lower band of the IPO issue price is higher than the market capitalization of the 200th company in the top 200 list provided by NPS Trust. The IPO company should get its stocks listed on either the BSE or NSE. These rules limit the pension fund managers from investing in IPO's of small and mid-sized companies and come in a protection measure (Srivats, 2021b).

Indirectly quoting the successful IPO of the loss-making food delivery

service provider Zomato, the Chairman of PFRDA, said that the regulator would not have any objection for pension funds to invest in such companies if the fund managers wish to do so (Srivats, 2021c).

PFRDA, over the years, has expanded the list of financial instruments into which pension funds can invest. It has recently allowed investment in new-age assets, such as Real Estate Investment Trusts (REIT) and Infrastructure Investment Trust (InvIT) so that the schemes can maintain a decent rate of return because interest rates have plunged to record lows. The regulator has urged fund managers to consider the risks involved and the liquidity available in those investments before taking any such decision. Newer and more varied products give cushion and better diversification opportunities for the fund managers (D. Saikat, 2021). PFRDA earlier allowed companies with a market capitalization of over Rs. 5,000 crores which are trading in the futures and options (F&O) segment of the market. This norm was later tweaked to allow investments in companies in the Top 200 list.

NPS NAV already considers the Mark-To-Market (MTM) valuation method, which reflects “the actual releasable value of investments despite holding funds of long-term investors.” This brings transparency and fairness to the subscribers.

PFRDA is also considering allowing 100 percent investment in the Equity asset class in Tier-II accounts. The current limit is at 75 percent. Once this is allowed, more subscribers will invest in NPS because it would become the lowest-cost equity product available for Indian investors. Tier-II accounts allow investment and withdrawals at any time without any lock-in.

L. Investing in Startups

PFRDA is not immediately keen on allowing NPS funds into startups. While the idea is not entirely off the table, the regulator is considering valuation-related issues. The clarification came out with some reports emerging in the media that startups will be funded with monies from the Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) and the Employees’ Provident Fund Organisation (EPFO). Unlike LIC and EPFO, NPS values the investments and discloses the Net Asset Value (NAV) daily. Arriving at the NAV rate will involve the valuation of underlying assets, and unfortunately, the metrics and measures currently available to value startups are inadequate.

M. Increase in FDI limits

The pension regulator recommended raising the Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) limit in pension fund houses from 49 percent to 74 percent. The Government of India approved the proposal. Increased fund flows will bolster

the structure and functioning of pension fund service providers and thereby leads to their long-term sustainability (Manohar, 2021). Both academic studies and industry experts believe that an increased number of fund houses will lead to increased competition, which benefits investors (MoneyControl, 2021). The FDI limit in insurance has been hiked to 74 percent in March 2021 by an Insurance Amendment Act 2021 amendment.

N. On-tap licensing for pension fund managers

Since July 2021, PFRDA has brought in on-tap licensing for pension fund managers on similar lines to the RBI. The RBI is allowing new banking entrants on the tap. Axis Bank is getting ready to formally offer its pension fund services, having its application was approved. With this, the total number of pension fund managers to eight. There are two more proposals before the committee. Once they get approval, the year 2021 would even end up with ten pension fund managers.

7. SCOPE FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

The following are some specific topics that are almost not covered by previous researchers and are worth studying by future researchers in the Indian context:

1. Competition amongst pension fund houses
2. Governance structures of pension fund houses
3. Correlation studies on macro-economic variables and stock market-specific variables compared against pension funds
4. Correlation studies involving mutual funds in general, and retirement funds (of mutual funds) in particular, as against NPS

8. CONCLUSIONS

The National Pension Scheme (NPS) of India has witnessed the introduction of regulations that has fostered the development of the pension fund system in the country. Individuals can now act as pension fund distributors. Penny drop helps in quicker subscriber verification and smoothens the withdrawal and exit phases from the pension system. NPS entry and exit age are changed to be more realistic owing to the increased life expectancy of Indians. Premature withdrawal norms are simplified. NPS fee hike makes existing pension fund houses probably break even in their business. Hiking FPI limits and On-tap licensing would bring in more new players and make existing fund houses well-capitalized and sustainable. Giving the nod to allow pension funds into IPOs can potentially boost returns. Overall, the various regulatory moves made by the PFRDA during

the year will make the National Pension Scheme (NPS) more robust and more relevant to various stakeholders of the pension fund ecosystem.

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